

Talking about Ronna Event Report

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Colophon

Project: VIVA-PLAN: A sustainable spatial planning framework for engaging diverse actors and citizens in revitalising in-between spaces for social inclusion, biodiversity, and well-being.

WP3: Develop and assess the effect of mosaic governance on attitudes toward revitalization.

Activity 3.1: Conduct a hack event in each study site.

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Photo courtesy of Emma Blomquist. Ronna Event: Work in groups. August 2021.

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Acknowledgments and contacts

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Summary

The concept of Mosaic Governance rests on relationships grounded in local context and puts forward ideas about how these relationships can be catalysed for transformative change. As part of the research project VIVA-PLAN we designed a Working Package where some of these assumptions have been put forward for further experimentation and testing. As part to this our project team partnered with a local NGO Läsförämlingsinstitutet for the organization of an on-site local stakeholder event which was held on the 25th of August 2021 in Södertälje (Sweden). The ambition for this event was to bring together ideas and insights from two different and now emerging engagement methods: i) **hackathons** and ii) **co-creation**, to create opportunity for discussion, visioning and local engagement. At this event, we shared data (summarised in data visualization sheets) collected in the course of our project about local conditions in Ronna, a residential area in Södertälje. In total, 15 participants attended the event, all affiliated with public or private organizations that are active in or near Ronna with a clear role and contribution to community building there. The event helped to unpack some of our findings and to further discuss challenges that emerged from data collection in Ronna. The event was a productive gathering where important questions were raised and discussed about challenges and opportunities of the Ronna residential area, and how they align with ideas about more sustainable living environments as currently advanced by Swedish planning policy.

1. Introduction

Governance of urban areas requires close collaboration across different sectors and areas of expertise, including municipal decision-makers, planners, managers and similar profiles who have a key role in the distribution of resources shaping the cities we live in. Over the past two decades, thoughts have been raised about the role of non-experts in urban governance, and how organized, and less organized, groups can contribute (Mattijssen et al, 2018). Models for alternative governance have been advanced (e.g., collaborative or polycentric), each emphasising some features over others. The model that is of interest to the research project VIVA-PLAN is **Mosaic Governance**, which is developed around the idea of enabling and giving space to active citizenship in urban governance (Buijs et al. 2018). Specifically, we are interested in how these ideas may be used to inform novel participatory methods and ways to engage those groups who traditionally are not involved in spatial planning, e.g., children, the elderly and migrants.

In the project VIVA-PLAN we work on participatory methods and bring together insights and ideas from different areas of work. Specifically, we use ideas underpinning two engagement methods: i) **hackathons** and ii) **co-creation**, in search for creating opportunities to engage diverse groups of people and stakeholders on discussions and visualisation about their living environments.

In the next section we first introduce the methods with a bit more detail, along with the participatory approach we used in our work. Then we provide background information about the Ronna Hack event our team organized in Södertälje, followed with a list of outcomes that emerged from the discussion. This report ends with some final considerations and ideas for future work and activities that could be of support to people, especially youth, living in Ronna.

2. To engage a diversity of expertise, values and needs

VIVA-Hack is an event that bring together insights from two different methods for citizen engagement: the **hackathon** (*speed problem solving events, often relying on technology*) and **co-creation** (*events where knowledge and expertise from a diversity of actors are appreciated and used on the task at hand*). Specifically, the VIVA-Hack aims to offer a platform for individual and social learning, by creating conditions for participants to work collaboratively on a challenge over a limited period of time while sharing their diverse experience, from a position of recognition that all experiences are valuable and needed. It is known that solutions to pressing issues that communities face are best developed within the local context and in collaboration with local actors. The VIVA-Hack seeks to be the platform where these conditions are put in place.

VIVA-Hack events were conducted in Ronna (Södertälje) and in Urbanplanen (Copenhagen) and were informed by a three-stage model (**Figure 1**). The first stage allowed us to develop understanding of the context, to map local issues as seen and described by the community itself and to develop relationships with local actors who understand local dynamics and the challenges present in the community. Through informal networking as well as structured social science studies, challenges and core social actors were identified, and the information collected was then used to organise the event. In the second stage, the challenge was raised for discussion and there was further exploration among VIVA-Hack participants, including actors from the private and public sector as well as activists in the area. At each event, we shared input to the participants in the form of qualitative and quantitative data, which participants used to develop questions and to collaboratively explore possible solutions to these. In the third stage, we conducted surveys with participants to identify main learnings from the event, and how the VIVA-Hack could be improved in future research and practice.

Figure 1. Three-step model informing the VIVA-Hack.

3. Ronna VIVA-Hacks

The aim of the VIVA-Hack about Ronna was to further discuss, identify, and explore *inequalities in accessing and shaping urban nature and meeting places in Ronna*. We held two separate events. The first event was an afternoon workshop with six local youth residents aged 15 to 16 years. We used a paper and pencil participatory mapping method to map and discuss places they like and dislike in Ronna and why, what they would like to be different, and what could make Ronna a more sustainable living environment for them. In addition, we asked the youth to put forward questions for discussion at the second VIVA-Hack event with local actors.

The second event was a full morning workshop with 15 local stakeholders, which we co-organized in collaboration with Läsförämningsinstitutet (LFI), a local association in Södertälje (See **Appendix 1** for day program). The event was a challenge-driven and co-creation event, where participants worked in small groups on three challenges. The challenges that we put forward for discussion were:

- 1)** *How can we make it easier for people to meet in and enjoy the neighbourhood and its green areas?*
- 2)** *What is needed to make young people feel welcomed in public places and when they spend time outdoors?*
- 3)** *How can we promote, support and enable young people's use of, access to, and opportunities to influence/shape public meeting places and green areas?*

The participants were presented with data visualization sheets to provide background and context, drawn partly from research conducted in the VIVA-PLAN project, partly from secondary data.

Infographic 1 (**Appendix 2**) shows the history, demography, and civil society of Ronna. Infographic 2 (**Appendix 3**) shows young people's access to public places and meeting places in Ronna, divided in green and gray infrastructure. Infographic 3 (**Appendix 4**) shows challenges young people face in the use of and opportunities to impact urban space in Ronna from an environmental justice perspective.

The session was facilitated so that the discussions were encouraged to be first ambitious and visionary and then narrowed down to what is feasible in terms of actions on the ground. This allowed the linking of ideal visions to what is feasible now, given current resources, possibilities, and capacities.

The work was moderated along three objectives: **a)** envisioning preferences (also representing inputs from day 1), **b)** exploring differences, and **c)** encouraging conformity.

- a) Envisioning Preferences:** Opening up to ideas and visions and allowing space for discussion on these in the group.
- b) Divergence:** See into where ideas and visions align well and where they do not, and which ones are more concreted than others.
- c) Convergence:** Narrowing down by indicating which ideas and visions are more concrete and workable.

4. Outcomes of the discussions

The three groups came up with a number of suggestions, ideas and further elaborations of the challenges and opportunities the Ronna community faces. Following the group discussions, all groups presented what they had discussed, and the suggestions, challenges and opportunities were discussed further in the whole group, evolving around the following broader themes:

- There is a lack of meeting places for recreational and socialisation needs for all ages, but for young people in particular. This could be addressed as part of long-term planning and policymaking.
- Suggestions and thoughts around physical and material resources to make residents enjoy urban space were accompanied with aspects of the low income-levels in Ronna, and how it often costs to be part of an organisation or use public space (e.g., to use the ice rink one needs ice skates).
- Incentives to participate in planning processes and try to influence the quality of outdoor environments risk being lower if one lacks basic security and faces more pressing issues, such as unemployment, health issues and low housing standards.
- Social aspects of spatial planning and use of public space are important, e.g., organised joint activities in the public realm. If social activities are organized in green areas, it can lower the thresholds for people to spend time there, as many seek social cohesion and sense of community and could be encouraged by these incentives.
- The non-profit sector needs (more) support and collaboration with public authorities to tune use of resources around local needs.
- Collaboration between different departments within the municipality could improve to be more attuned and more effective to cater to local needs in Ronna.
- There is lack of confidence in public authorities and thus a need to build enduring networks of trust.
- There is a challenge in upholding perseverance, continuity and long-term perspectives when working with short and fix-termed projects.

- Short term projects, without a permanent presence, are not able to keep the momentum and motivation for locals to be engaged. There is an under-explored potential in ways how residents could be more actively engaged.
- Many of the suggestions and ideas comes down to issues of costs, yet the general debate is less often about what economic and social *gains* there are to relocate resources and priorities.

5. Conclusions and recommendations

The event brought together different actors. Some interact and collaborate regularly while others do not. This diversity is of interest and proved useful when discussing challenges, as it allowed contextualization of the different perspectives that emerged. The idea of mosaic governance is rooted in social relations, and events when run productively may hold potential to strengthen such networks. The combination of a challenge-driven workshop and co-creation proved useful to create space for different voices and needs. We gathered that a majority of the participants had a positive and constructive experience of being able to talk to people from other organizations with other perspectives and angles than their own. They had the opportunity to learn how different organizations work with and approach these issues from their own opportunities and constraints. The VIVA-Hack contributed to networking and to open the conversation among formal and informal stakeholders, especially in the dialogue between formal actors (municipality, housing associations, the school) and informal actors (NGOs, tenants association), as they generally are rather separated. Some of the participants expressed that it felt productive to be able to discuss with each other, and that there should be more activities like this. At times during the discussions strong and somewhat frustrated feelings emerged, yet respectful and mostly constructive, as all in the room felt passionate about trying to find solutions to the challenges that the Ronna community face.

Overall, we conclude that the format for this event was well received and proved useful to the purpose at hand. The process design, where we first focused on visioning before moving on to what is more concrete and feasible for Ronna, was well suited. It allowed participants to think outside the box and simultaneously grounded the discussions in reality. Gatherings and events like these, which are inclusive, meaningful, and collaboratively oriented, may contribute to building well-functioning social networks and are as such a strategic tool to be deployed in urban governance. An interesting observation is that compared to some other strategic policy tools and events, the VIVA-Hacks have been less complex to organize and relatively cost-effective. Close collaboration with local actors and consideration to local needs provides opportunities to advance on the challenge of power-imbalances and inequalities in access to and opportunities to shape public meeting places and urban nature, where some groups commonly have less influence.

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Appendix 1: Day program 25th of August 2021

09:30-09:40 Welcome and introduction of VIVA-PLAN's project members

09:40-09:50 Presentation of the day

09:50-10:00 Review of materials and the challenges that form the basis of the discussions

10:00-11:00 Workshop and discussion about challenges

11:00-11:15 Coffee and refreshments

11:15-11:30 Presentations of what has been discussed

11:30-12:00 Rounding off

12:00-13:30 Lunch and continued conversations

Appendix 2: History, demography, and civil society of Ronna

See page 10.

Appendix 3: Young people's access to public places and meeting places in Ronna, divided in green and gray infrastructure

See page 11.

Appendix 4: Challenges young people face in the use of and opportunities to impact urban space in Ronna from an environmental justice perspective

See page 12.

HISTORY AND DEMOGRAPHICS OF

RONNA

1962

The first high-rise buildings from the Million Program in Ronna were completed. They hosted predominantly Finnish families who were economic migrants.

2021

≈ 8000 residents

1970s

The Assyrian/Syrian settlement begins. Following the immigration of the 21st century, Christian Assyrian/Syrian residents now make up the majority of the population in the district.

Ronna is on the Swedish Police's list of particularly vulnerable areas.

These are identified by e.g., low income levels, low education levels, above average unemployment, above average criminal activity, low voter turnouts.

HOWEVER: Negative framing of the area = risk of increased marginalization?

Of which **27%** are 0-19 years (compared to 23% in Sweden)

34 % of households are 1-2 adults with children (compared to 29% in Sweden)

- In Sweden, researchers have argued that there are knowledge gaps and lack of nuanced societal analyzes of vulnerable areas (Gerell et al. 2020).

- The Police's list of vulnerable areas has in 2021 been reviewed by The National Audit Office, which states that the methods for identifying the areas are partly based on the local police's subjective estimates of the area's challenges (Government Letter 2020/21: 108, p. 6).

- Ronna has also been described as **"cosy, leafy, an idyll"** and **"visually and socially attractive, a friendly and beautiful place"** (Mack, 2021, p. 1).

ORGANISATIONS & CIVIL SOCIETY

- 1 public school
- 4 public kindergartens
- 1 youth center

Södertälje has **251** registered associations. Less than **5 %** are found in Ronna.

No associations work specifically with green areas and access to urban nature.

The Syrian Orthodox church has a strong position.

Holds a popular scout organisation for local youth.

- Initiatives exist to:
- Engage young people in various activities
 - Increase the number of young people who are engaged in sports
 - Increase the presence of girls in public space

Less than **50 %** aged **7-25** are active in a sports association.

YOUNG PEOPLE'S ACCESS TO PUBLIC PLACES, NATURE AND RECREATION IN RONNA

MEETING PLACES
(Often with both green and gray infrastructure)

Green infrastructure

Nature areas in the city, all forms of vegetation. Provides biodiversity and ecosystem services.

FORESTS

- Coniferous and mixed forests that surround Ronna from north and west.
- Additionally, in Ronna's built-up area there are 14 ha of forest.
- The forest does not appear to be well-visited by teenagers.

GREEN "IN-BETWEEN AREAS"

- Green areas in-between buildings, e.g., lawns with or without trees or shrubs, meadow-like open vegetation, planted shrubbery, avenues, flower beds.
- Can be experienced as "forgotten space" and have an unclear value for residents, municipalities and property owners.
- More meeting places in-between residential areas and in central Ronna are requested by residents.

LINA NATURE RESERVE

- Hiking area with deciduous groves, mixed forests, pastures.
- Perceived as difficult to access from Ronna.
- Does not appear to be well-visited by teenagers.

Research shows that contact with nature for urban residents promotes physical and mental health (Maas et al. 2008, 2009).

Gray infrastructure

Does not consist of nature but is made of humanly produced or processed materials, such as concrete or asphalt.

RONNA SCHOOL

- Schoolyard and multi-functional sports facility built in 2010.
- Popular meeting place for young people and others, many various activities.

PLAYGROUNDS AND KINDERGARTENS

- Places where teenagers spend time but are intended for younger children.
- Experiences by youth of not feeling welcomed in these places.

SOCCER FIELDS AND BASKETBALL COURTS

- Popular to use among young people.
- Many outdoor facilities, fields and courts are experienced as worn.

RÖSBERGA YOUTH CENTER

- Popular place for young people, during the pandemic few have been able to be there.
- Perceived as difficult to access, the path there leads through an unlit forest area.
- Large gravel plane outside the building with unclear function.

RONNA CENTRUM

- Privately owned.
- Not much green infrastructure.
- Safe or unsafe place for young people? Differing experiences of this.

Research shows that young people in Sweden spend more time indoors (Elinder et al. 2014, Pagels et al. 2014), which affects both physical activity and socialization and may deteriorate physical and mental health in the short and long term (LeBlanc et al. 2015, Weimann et al. 2015, WHO 2010).

CHALLENGES YOUNG PEOPLE FACE IN THE USE OF AND OPPORTUNITIES TO IMPACT URBAN SPACE IN RONNA

RESEARCH ELSEWHERE SHOWS THAT

Young people use public spaces differently than other groups, and despite the great impact that urban planning has on youth, they have relatively limited influence on decisions that affect their living environments (Freeman 2019, Osborne et al. 2017).

Young people are often seen as a disturbing element in urban environments (Jackie 2014, Molnar et al. 2004).

Residents in socio-economically challenged areas has less access to high quality green space and public meeting places and less opportunities to influence urban planning and decision-making (Anguelovski et al. 2020, Mack 2021).